

THE BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RESEARCH TREND ABOUT PARENTING THE EARLY CHILDHOOD CHILDREN

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The Bibliometric Analysis of the Research Trend About Parenting the Early Childhood Children

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Abstract

Many researchers took the scope of parenting. However, specific information about the publication trend or research focus on parenting early childhood children is limited. This research revealed the most prominent research topics and trends in parenting early childhood children from 2000 to 2023. This research is important to determine the reviewed topics and the gaps and provide insight for further research development. Thus, new innovations and research opportunities for early childhood parenting will be more frequent. This research method applied bibliometric analysis with publish or perish application, PoP. The applied keywords were adjusted to the research focus and objective, such as "research parenting," "research parental", and "early childhood," published from 2000-2023. The research results found that the population increase from the published articles was significantly related to parenting or parenting early childhood children from 2016 until the present day. Then, based on the mode of network visualization display, the researcher found 72 items of 5 clusters: childhood education, achievement, behavior, parenting, and challenge. This research found that parenting early childhood children was done by school teachers instead of the parents. The interpreted descriptions lead to limited research on parenting in early childhood. Thus, future researchers could promote research on this topic or focus, such as parenting or parenting style, parenting programs, and parenting done by fathers.

Keywords: *bibliometric, parenting, early childhood children, research trend*

Introduction

Parenting is an important factor to consider by parents because it influences the excellent growth and development of children. Therefore, nurturing children must be adjusted to the developmental stages of the children. One of the important developments to consider is the early childhood period. Early childhood children are children aged between 2 and 7 years old. In this phase, children could develop their skills to think before action, to understand and follow the given instructions, and to participate in planning and solving simple problems that contribute to the development of children in terms of behavioral competence, pre-academic skill achievement, and social relationship (Willoughby & Hudson, 2023).

Parents must nurture early childhood children because this matter influences the children's future development. This phase is a golden phase because the brain develops from 50% to 80%, the highest one in their life (Handayani, 2021). Early childhood parenting is strongly correlated to children's cognition, behavior, and health (Chen et al., 2023). Therefore, risky families or families with problems may suffer from adverse impacts due to the adjustment during childhood. This matter could last until adolescence (Seay et al., 2023).

An aspect with vast development in this phase is the cognition of children. Research about brain development points out that the brain develops quickly in the first three years of life. Therefore, the brain could be stimulated to develop. Children without excellent environmental stimulation will have smaller brains and less normal brains than normal children at their age (Shonkoff & Phillips, 2000). Based on Piaget's cognitive theory, early childhood children within the pre-operational phase can imagine objects or unseen events, determine incorrect or correct thoughts based on their personal points of view, and create objects (Putra, 2022).

Besides the cognitive aspect, the nurturing done by parents could also influence children's social and emotional aspects. This aspect deals with children's opportunities for their future development, academic impacts, and behaviors (Tamblyn et al., 2023). Children with excellent socio-emotional skills also have excellent learning skills, self-control, and socio-interpersonal skills (Lee & Gleespen, 2023). Poor emotional and social conditions for children are primarily observable when the children receive authoritarian parenting (Agbaria & Mahamid, 2023). Parents with authoritarian parenting are observable from the rigid habit and punishment implementation. This parenting style does not provide freedom of expression for children because the parents want the children to meet their expectations. This situation makes the children unhappy, depressed, anxious, frightened, and less communicative (Camisasca, 2022; Flamant et al., 2024; Roşca, 2024).

The other aspects include physics, morality, and language, which grow along with the children's development and age. The urgency of the physical and motor skills of children is important for the initial development of each child. This condition influences various health aspects of children (Dwiyanti et al., 2023). From a moral aspect, the father's participation is instrumental in nurturing children, such as monitoring the children, giving punishment, and making influential decisions related to the moral development of children (Safitri et al., 2021). From the language aspect, the linguistic skill of early childhood children begins with an initial letter introduction. Children use language to communicate their ideas, exchange information, and develop inter-individual relationships. Linguistic skill refers to a communicational meaning with other individuals (Dwiyanti et al., 2023). Based on these conditions, parental parenting for early childhood children influences the development of children even until their future.

Although early childhood parenting requires parents' physical presence, some conditions do not allow parents to be fully involved in

nurturing their children. An example is - when mothers are fully working. On the other hand, the early childhood children require the presence of the mothers. Naturally, mothers are highly involved in nurturing their children (Chen et al., 2023). Therefore, early childhood children by parenting mothers require excellent time management. Mothers must share their commitments to working and parenting their families so that the children can receive full necessities (Handayani, 2024).

Mothers who are highly involved in nurturing their children also need their fathers to participate. Children with parenting patterns from two parents have optimum development and growth. Moreover, for families in which the fathers and mothers are working. Fathers could support their mothers by also nurturing the children. This harmony should also receive some support and actions of a collaborative team without any competition, even if the roles are different (Muafiah et al., 2019). The participation of mothers and fathers during childhood is important and helpful in preventing problematic behaviors during the adolescent period (Yang et al., 2024).

The reality in society shows that fathers do not frequently participate in nurturing their children. Paquette et al. (2023) found that limited studies put their focus on the correlation between parents and children in managing the risk to children. They also found no studies put their focus on the relationship between fathers and children. In Indonesia, a lack of father participation in nurturing children occurs due to the belief culture in society. Chen, Fu, and Yiu (2019) explain that cultures, norms, and applied social values determine parental practices and patterns. The presence of patriarchal culture influences child parenting. Patriarchal perceives males as the dominant party and ignores the roles of women within the social arrangement. These matters lead to discrimination (Rahmayanty et al., 2023). This condition influences the job descriptions between fathers and mothers. In this culture, all domestic tasks, including nurturing children or parenting, are the tasks of mothers, while the fathers deal with public matters.

Besides cultures, genders also influence parenting differences by parents. Sofiani et al. (2020) found that biased gender parenting patterns for early childhood children were mostly observable in authoritarian parenting styles. The observable gender bias includes the stigma that female and male children must have specific behaviors and actions differently. This matter leads to jealousy toward children, lack of self-confidence, emotional interruption, personal and other individual comparison, and rebellion.

Basically, the excellent development of children could run properly by implementing mindful parenting. The nurturing patterns refer to how parents interact with children to guide and educate them so their characters and knowledge can be developed (Fatmawati et al., 2021). Mindful parenting is the nurturing pattern when the parents present and share their love, act wisely, communicate excellently, and share their empathy (Handayani, 2019). Many parents believe the greatest responsibility in nurturing children is facilitating and providing relevant necessities. However, children need many things beyond this matter (Dhio & Fono, 2021)

The early childhood period is essential for stimulating developmental aspects. This period provides the basic matter for a better future for the children. However, problematic behaviors of early childhood children become risky factors for future life problems and interruptions. Therefore, parenting for early childhood children should receive more attention. This research is vital to determine the reviewed topics and the gaps and provide insight for further research development. Thus, new innovations and research opportunities dealing with early childhood parenting will be more frequent. The efforts to determine the publication trend related to early childhood parenting are done with bibliometrics.

Bibliometric is a method to analyze publications statistically (Wang et al., 2021; Phoong et al., 2022) and to determine the widespread and significant publications within certain fields (Yigit & Çakmak, 2024).

Research Questions

Based on this matter, many researchers studied parenting or parenting. However, the researchers found limited specific information about the publication trend or the research focus for early childhood children. Thus, this research specifically sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the trends related to early childhood children from 2000 to 2023?
2. What are the most appealing research topics and trends with the scope of parenting early childhood children from 2000-2023?
3. Who are the most frequent researchers to publish articles about parenting early childhood children are published from 2000 to 2023?

Methodology

Research Design

This research method applied bibliometric analysis with publish or perish application, PoP. Bibliometric is a crucial method to analyze subjects of publications qualitatively or quantitatively (Abouzid et al., 2021). The quantitative analyses include the publication trend, the annual citation average, the top keyword, the nationality of the author, and the top journal. On the other hand, the qualitative analyses cover the most cited documents by categorizing the documents into executive functional components, related variables, instruments, and samples (Heidary et al., 2024).

The researcher took the data on Monday, January 1, 2024. In this research, the researcher applied careful bibliometric analysis in five stages: selecting data, selecting keywords, creating matrix connections, visualizing the results, and interpreting the data (Kristial, 2021).

Procedure

The initial step began with collecting the articles from cross reference or crossreff. Then, the researchers began to group the ranges from 2000 to 2023 with the adjusted keywords and research focus, such as “research parenting” and “early childhood.” Then, the researchers screened the articles and analyzed only the eligible articles. The analysis was useful in finding out the results of the yearly publication counted with Microsoft Excel software. On the other hand, in visualizing the bibliometric results, the researchers processed the data with Vos Viewer. This Vos viewer facilitates researchers in determining the frequently appearing topics related to parenting early childhood children and authors with high research frequency on the topic. The final step was interpreting the obtained data related to the research topic. Presented below is the data-collecting process.

Results and Discussion

The researcher found the data with some applied keywords, such as “research parenting,” “research parental,” and “early childhood” from 2000 to 2023. Figure 2 shows the results.

Based on the analysis, the researcher found 904 articles. Then, the researchers screened the articles to obtain articles written in English without any duplications. This process led to 774 articles. The final step was analyzing the articles.

Figure 1. The metadata tracing process with PoP

The Publication Trend

Based on the article tracing process from 2000 to 2023, the researchers found the lowest article publications were in 2011, 15 articles; on the other hand, the most published articles were in 2023, 70 articles. The research results found the population increment from the published articles significantly related to parenting or parenting early childhood children from 2016 until the present day. The evidence was the publication number while exploring the metadata with PoP and the overlay visualization of the research trend about early childhood parenting. This matter showed that parental awareness about parenting early childhood children was excellent. Maftuchatunni'mah & Nasir (2022); and Sholichah, Ayuningrum, & Afif (2021); found that parenting was effective in improving parental awareness to nurture early childhood children. However, the highest increment related to the topic occurred from 2019 to 2020 with 18 published articles. Table 1 shows the publication tracing results of the articles.

Table 1. The number of published articles related to early childhood children from 2000 to 2023

Year	Publication Numbers	Percentage
2000	18	2,30%
2001	21	2,68%
2002	19	2,42%
2003	34	4,34%
2004	27	3,44%
2005	26	3,32%
2006	30	3,83%
2007	18	2,30%
2008	22	2,81%
2009	18	2,30%
2010	16	2,04%
2011	15	1,91%
2012	22	2,81%
2013	32	4,08%
2014	27	3,44%
2015	30	3,83%
2016	34	4,34%
2017	37	4,72%
2018	36	4,59%
2019	43	5,48%
2020	61	7,78%
2021	61	7,78%
2022	67	8,55%
2023	70	8,93%

The Most Appealing Research Topic

Based on the visualization of Vos Viewer mode, the overlay visualization describes the research historical traces with similar results. Figure 2 shows that since 2015, many researchers have taken the topic of early childhood children. However, the researchers found different research trends in 2016 and 2020. In 2016, most research, indicated with purple colors and circles, focused on early childhood terms, education, teacher, and mother. However, in 2020, most research indicated yellow colors and large circles, which is new research with a focus on parenting style. The terms father and parenting program indicated with green colors, show the topics have rare discussions although they are not new topics. Some research about child parenting by fathers were done by (Shafer, 2021; Yang, et al. 2024; Muafiah, et al. 2019; Petts, et al. 2020). The results indicate that mothers promote more frequent child parenting than fathers.

Figure 2. Overlay visualization of the research trend on parenting early childhood children

Based on the network visualization display, the researchers analyzed the data to determine the network strength among the terms. Figure 4 shows that early childhood education has a strong association with teachers and mothers. Besides that, early childhood education also significantly grows along with parenting programs and parenting styles. This result shows that most researches about early childhood children are correlated to school education by the teachers. On the other hand, the topic of parenting is mostly discussed about parenting programs and parenting styles done by mothers.

The large circles represent the strong correlations while the small circles indicate low correlations. These situations show the research gaps to fill in the future. For example, the father's parenting. The research results found that father parenting influenced cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioral developments (Diniz et al., 2021). Taking some leave, taking 2-week leave, or taking any leave done by fathers are positively correlated to children's perception toward the father participation, father-child intimacy, and father-child communication (Petts, et al. 2020). Besides that, the parenting styles between fathers and mothers could influence the children's development in the future (Yaffe, 2023).

Figure 3. The network visualization of the topic of parenting early childhood children

Based on the display mode of the network visualization, the researchers found 72 items from 5 clusters, starting from childhood education, achievement, behavior, parenting, and challenge. Based on the findings, the first research focus is on childhood education. Research about parenting early childhood children tends to take early childhood education at schools or relevant to learning. From the first cluster, the content of the term tends to be the learning activities at schools, such as classroom, early childhood classroom, early childhood education, educator, experience, and play. Lessons for early childhood are mostly done in the context of playing. This finding is observable in the research of Kesalainen et al. (2022), who explains that playing benefits the education and development of children. Children who will enter formal learning also have high participation and motivation (Alharbi & Alzahrani, 2020). Dodd, Nesbit, and Gibbon (2023) explain the implementation of adventuring provides learning opportunities to prevent mental health problems in children.

The second cluster is about achievement, consisting of parenting practice, parenting stress, self-efficacy, stress, and support. These findings indicate the importance of excellent parenting with excellent parenting training (Kakhki et al., 2022; Fernandes et al., 2022), excellent belief to promote parenting (Zhang et al., 2024), and the support needed (Sanders, 2023; Zhang et al., et al., 2024). In this condition, fathers or mothers may suffer from stress while nurturing their children (Mikolajczak et al., 2021; McDaniel & Radesky, 2018; Spinelli et al., 2021). Therefore, emotional management efforts while nurturing or parenting are important to prevent victims from the children due to the bad emotions of the parents. (Fernandes et al, 2022) found that the effectiveness of Mindful Moment parenting training could encourage mothers from the intervention group to relieve the stress of burdening parenting, improve dispositional attention, and decrease their perceptions about the temperamental attitudes of the toddlers.

The third cluster is about behavior, starting from term cognitive development, discipline, early age, independence, parenting program, parenting style, preschool, problem, responsibility, and style. Based on these findings, the researchers found that research about nurturing early childhood children included parenting styles and parenting programs with certain behaviors such as discipline, independence, and responsibility. Excellent parenting could influence positive behavior and vice versa. Chen et al. (2023) found that early childhood parenting strongly influences children's cognitive and behavioral skills and health. Emotional regulation of parents could also influence self-adjustment and behavior in parenting children Camisasca et al. (2022). Inconsistent parenting correlates with children's dietary patterns, such as dietary patterns with high emotion, high dietary patterns, and difficulty eating (Leuba et al., 2022).

The fourth cluster of caring deals with early childhood education, early childhood settings, early childhood teaching, and kindergarten. The fourth cluster shows early childhood parenting with educational orientation and school for children. In this domain, early childhood children must receive education about caring. Besides the caring attitude taught by teachers in daily activities, this attitude can be observed when the children are having activities outside. The outdoor activities could be outing classes to develop a caring attitude toward the environment (Septarina et al., 2022). In this case, children identify the importance of their emotions, actions, relationships, and environment to realize excellent well-being.

The last cluster is about challenges, consisting of community terms, contributions, early childhood research, and early years. Early childhood parenting has some challenges because not many people understand early childhood parenting practices. Pearson, Rawdin, and Ahuja (2023) found the importance of a specific workforce with adaptive capability to carry out the early childhood program and certain communities about early childhood parenting—however, some drawbacks found on early childhood parenting givers due to low and complex human resources. Suryati et al. (2023) found that early childhood education institutions attempted to maximize the roles of parents, but they could not. Based on the explanation, training about parenting early childhood children is important.

In this fifth cluster, the researchers also found the term of society. Based on the related research about early childhood children and the community, parents' environment and society could influence the development of children due to community participation (Wahyudin, 2022). In Indonesia, this participation is observable from the Integrated Service Agency, “posyandu” (Pos Pelayanan Terpadu) (Islami et al., 2023). The integrated service unit becomes the health effort of the community. The management of this institution is from and for the community to empower and facilitate the community in gaining health access (Tulloh et al., 2020). Pearson, Rawdin, and Ahuja (2023) also found that training for the village communicators based on the Indian society could support the improvement of local relevance and early childhood service effectiveness. In this case, parents of early childhood children could find the benefits of the given programs by the village communicators. The research with the theme of parenting early childhood children

Table 2 shows the consistent researchers with the investigation on early childhood from the research results.

Table 2. Most researchers studied early childhood children

<i>Selected</i>	<i>Author</i>	<i>Documents</i>	<i>Total Link Strength</i>
	bertram, tony	5	0
	diamond, karen e	7	0
	diamond, karen e.	7	0
	hyzon, marion c	5	0
	maranatha, jojor renta	5	0
	putri, suci utami	5	0
	rettew, david	14	0
	vandenbroeck, michel	7	0

The interesting matter is - a researcher from Indonesia named Putri Suci Utami. Based on the tracing process on Google Scholar, the researchers found that Putri dominantly took researchers focusing on early childhood and classroom learning. Putri's articles are Steam-PBL, a problem-solving strategy to solve problems of early childhood children (Putri & Taqjudin, 2022) and the identification of fluency in early childhood children with STEM-project-based learning for early childhood children (Putri & Pitria, 2022).

Based on the findings, the research is mostly about parenting early childhood children which school teachers mostly did. Therefore, researchers about how parents nurture children are limited. This matter becomes the gap to fill, for example with parenting programs, parenting style, and parenting style by fathers.

Conclusion

Parenting is an essential factor to consider by parents because it influences the excellent growth and development of children. Based on the results, the researchers found 1) The related publication trend with increased published article numbers about early childhood parenting from 2016 until now. The evidence was the publication number while exploring the metadata with PoP and the overlay visualization of the research trend about early childhood parenting. This matter shows the increased awareness of early childhood parenting. 2). The most observable topic is grouped into 5 clusters. These clusters are childhood education, achievement, behavior, parenting, and challenge. Based on the findings, primary school teachers tend to promote research about early childhood parenting. 3). One of the consistent research studies is on the theme of early childhood parenting from Indonesia by Putri Suci Utami. However, the exploration with Google Scholar found that Putri is dominant in conducting research on the topic of early childhood children with classroom learning concentration.

Based on the conclusion, the researchers recommend: 1) To use these findings as the descriptions of limited research on early childhood parenting. Therefore, future researchers could promote the same research topic, starting with parenting style, parenting programs, and parenting by fathers. 2). Based on the research results, the researchers found the researchers' awareness about the importance of early childhood parenting. However, parents seem not to understand this parenting style, so studies about parenting practices are important for developing products, such as parenting training modules. 3). Research about the efforts of stimulating the children's development by schools and teachers is frequently observable to support the school programs. Therefore, cooperation among teachers and parents is important to develop the children optimally.

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